

Internet Protocol (IPv4) in Respect of Controlled Environment of an Organization

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Abstract—The IPv4 and IPv6 are the only Internetworking protocols most organizations in the world are using for even their internal usage. These protocols were basically designed for use in the Internet domain. In spite of their robustness and efficiency, there are a few points which can be of interest to an organization for customizing according to its needs. This paper discusses the Header format of IPv4 in light of the specific requirements of an organization and suggests some alterations that can be considered for optimizing the Header.

Keywords—IPv4; protocol; header format; networking;

I. INTRODUCTION

IPv4 means Internetworking Protocol version 4. IPv4 is a Network Layer (Layer 3) protocol and is the main protocol behind all the data transfer done over Internet using various applications like Email, Web Browsing, social networking like Facebook, WhatsApp, etc. Data are transferred and shared in the form of packets. IPv4 is described in [1], replacing [2] which was used to define IPv4 earlier. IPv4 is connectionless protocol and uses Datagram service.

Though the IPv4 fulfills almost all the requirements when it comes to the internet usage of an organization, it seems that for the internal networking for an organization it is an overkill. In this paper we present the details of the header of IPv4 along with point wise proposal to make the header lighter for a small organization.

II. IPV4 HEADER FORMAT

An IPv4 datagram consists of two parts viz. the header part and the body or payload part [3]. The header in turn has a fixed part of 20 bytes and a variable part which contains options and padding. The format of IPv4 header is given in Figure. 1.

VER	HLEN	Type of Service	Total Length	
Identification Bits				Fragment Offset
Time To Live	Protocol	Header Checksum		
Source IP Address				
Destination Address				
Options and Padding				

Figure. 1. IPv4 header.

Each of the fields is not essential for a small organization as the usage of a computer network depends on the workload and its type. So, it can be interesting to explore various fields for their usage and applicability.

III. IPV4 HEADER FIELDS

The various fields of the IPv4 header along with the modification proposals are given in the following subsections:

A. Version field

This field gives the version of protocol of the IPv4 packet. It uses 4 bits and caters till version number 15. Popular versions are version 4 and version 6. In case of a small organization, these can be reduced to 2 bits only i.e. only 4 possible versions. This is justified as the change in versions does not happen rapidly. Moreover we can remap the version from 00 for version 4 and 01 for version 6.

B. HLEN field

HLEN refers to Header Length which is variable because of the availability of various Options that we'll cover subsequently. Its value is taken in 32-bit words. The minimum value is 5 which corresponds to 20 bytes – the case when no options are used. Since HLEN is 4-bit field, its maximum value is 15 which corresponds to 60 byte.

The Options field, thus gets maximum of 40 byte space in the datagram header. Since most of the Datagrams do not have any options, this field can be dropped altogether i.e. 0 bits.

C. Type of Service fields

Figure. 2 depicts the Type of Service (TOS) field. TOS field differentiates between classes of service. It uses reliability and speed in various combinations. For some application like real-time voice/video communication, speed of delivery is preferred, whereas, in applications like file transfer, accuracy is more desirable.

Figure. 2. Type of Service (TOS) field.

Subsequently, the TOS field was modified to include differentiated services. The new format is shown in Fig. 3 below. Six bits of the DS field are used as a code point (DSCP) to select the Per Hop Behavior (PHB) a packet experiences at each node. These service classes include the four queuing priorities, three discard probabilities and the historical classes. Last two bits are used to indicate Explicit Congestion Notification (ECN).

Fig. 3. Differentiated Services (DS) Field

If we observe carefully, we can make out that this field is not essential and can be dropped as in a controlled environment they are not used at all.

D. Total Length field

This field gives the total length of the datagram, taking into account both the length of the header and the data. Being 16 bit field, it can give the maximum value of 65,535 bytes hence limiting the packet length to the same i.e. 65,535 bytes. Since in all datagrams, the payload has to be within a frame of 1500 bytes of Ethernet, this field can be reduced to 12 bits.

E. Identification field

Identification field tells the destination host which datagram the newly arrived fragment belongs to. The value is assigned by the sender. The value in the identification field is the same for all the fragments of a datagram. This field is also not essential. This is based on our experience that it is never required to fragment the payload for small collision domain.

F. Flags

There are various Control Flags as given below:

- Bit 0: reserved, must be zero
- Bit 1: (DF) 0 = May Fragment, 1 = Don't Fragment.

For example, for transfer of memory image when computer boots, its ROM might ask for a memory image to be sent to it as a single datagram. In this case, the packet may have to take suboptimal route. As a rule, all machines are required to accept fragments of 576 bytes or less.

- Bit 2: (MF) 0 = Last Fragment, 1 = More Fragments. MF (More Fragment) flag has its bit set for all fragments except the last fragment and helps in reassembly of the datagram.

This field is also not essential.

G. Fragment Offset field

- This field tells where in the current datagram this fragment belongs.
- All fragments (except the last one) in a datagram have to be multiple of 8 bytes which is the elementary fragment unit.
- It is 13-bit field, so it has maximum 8192 fragments per datagram. Thus, maximum datagram length of 65,536 bytes, one more than the Total length field.

Since the datagram is not fragmented, this field is also not required.

H. Time to Live (TTL) field

This field is a counter and is used to limit packet lifetimes. Its value is decremented on each hop and has maximum lifetime of 255 hops. When TTL counter hits 0, the packet is discarded and a warning packet is sent back to the source host. This feature prevents datagram from wandering around forever e.g. in case routing tables gets corrupted.

In case of small to small-medium organizations, the maximum number of routers between two end points is around 4, and hence this field can be reduced to 3 bits.

I. Protocol field

Protocol field tells the network layer which transport process to give the datagram after the network layer has assembled a complete datagram e.g. TCP, UDP, etc. Protocols and other assigned numbers are contained in an online database which is located at www.iana.org.

In case of common organizations we use only TCP and may be some times UDP. So this field can be safely reduced to 1 bit with remapping of value as 0 for TCP and 1 for UDP.

J. Header Checksum field

This field verifies the header and is useful for detecting errors generated by bad memory words inside a router. The

algorithm is to add up all the 16-bit half words as they arrive, using one's compliment arithmetic and then take the one's compliment of the result.

Header checksum is assumed to be zero upon arrival. This algorithm is more robust than using a normal add. Header checksum is recomputed at each hop because at least one field always changes viz. *TTL*.

Instead of going for 16 bits checksum, it is more than enough to dedicate 12 bits for the purpose.

K. Source Address / Destination Address

This indicates the network number and host number of the source and destination hosts. It is of 32 bits. Earlier the IP addressing was in the format of *classful addressing* which was subsequently changed and Classless InterDomain Routing was adopted [4].

This provided a way to conveniently allocate contiguous address ranges that contained more than 255 hosts but fewer than 65,536. That is, something other than single class B or multiple class C network numbers could be allocated to sites. Using CIDR, any address range is not predefined as being part of a class but instead requires a mask similar to a subnet mask, sometimes called a CIDR mask. CIDR masks are not limited to a site but are instead visible to the global routing system. Thus, the core Internet routers must be able to interpret and process masks in addition to network numbers. This combination of numbers, called a network prefix, is used for both IPv4 and IPv6 address management [5].

Since the organization is small and number of collision domains is also very small, we always use class C addresses only. This suggests that it would suffice to use only two bytes for source address and two bytes for destination address with upper byte to represent network address and lower byte the host.

L. Options field

Keeping *Options* allows subsequent versions of protocol to include information not present in the original protocol. It is kept to permit experimenters to try out new ideas, and to avoid allocating header bits to information that is rarely needed. This is a variable length field. Each Option begins with a 1-byte code identifying the Option (Identifier). Some options are followed by a 1-byte option length and then one or more data bytes.

Options field is padded out to a multiple of 4 bytes. Initially, there were the following five options to which subsequently more were added:

- (i). Security: Specifies how secret the datagram is.
- (ii). Strict source routing: Gives complete path to be followed.

- (iii). Loose source routing: Gives a list of routers not to be missed.
- (iv). Record route: Makes each router append its IP address.
- (v). Timestamp: Makes each router append its address and timestamp.

Since options are not used in all datagrams, this field is not used.

M. The Proposed Header Format

In view of the foregoing, we propose the modified IPv4 header format as given in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Modified IPv4 Header

It is of total 8 bytes only. It means that with every datagram we save at least 12 bytes due to header only. For a small organization to small-medium organization, this saving would yield better throughput. We came to the proposed header format after carefully observing the network traffic and analyzing the IP packets of around 250 hosts distributed across six separate collision domains.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Postel, "Internet Protocol," Internet RFC 0791/STD 0005, Sept. 1981.
- [2] J. Postel, "Internet Protocol," Internet RFC 0760, January 1980.
- [3] Andrew S. Tanenbaum and David J. Wetherall, "Computer Networks", 5th edition, Prentice Hall, 2010.
- [4] V. Fuller and T. Li, "Classless Inter-domain Routing (CIDR): The Internet Address Assignment and Aggregation Plan," Internet RFC 4632/BCP 0122, Aug. 2006.
- [5] Kevin R. Fall and W. Richard Stevens, "TCP/IP Illustrated, Volume 1: The Protocols", 2nd edition, Addison-Wesley Professional, 2011,

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